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Correlation between manufacturing processes and anisotropic
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Abstract

We present an original, easy to implement, reliable method of non-destructive testing of the orientation of carbon nanotubes by magnetic moment measurements performed in three perpendicular directions of magnetic field. Multi-wall carbon nanotubes/polystyrene composites were prepared by stretching and forge-rolling methods with the same nanotube loading. Unusually strong diamagnetic anisotropy in the composites prepared by the stretching method was observed and attributed to an additional diamagnetic response from the polystyrene aromatic rings wrapping the nanotubes. Strong anisotropy of diamagnetic susceptibility of the composites with highly aligned nanotubes correlates with anisotropic electromagnetic response and with improved microwave absorption properties. Both magnetic anisotropy and microwave absorbance is considerably lower in the composites prepared by the forge-rolled method. The magnetic results correlate well with polarized Raman spectroscopy. The research findings contribute to a better understanding of nanotube-polymer interface, alignment mechanisms, and ultimately the optimal design and performance of functional nanotube - aromatic polymer nanocomposites.

Keywords A. Polymer-matrix composites; B. Directional orientation; B. Magnetic properties; C. Non-destructive testing.

1. Introduction

Extraordinary mechanical, thermal and electronic properties of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) make them ideal fillers for composites used in many practical areas. One of areas is electromagnetic shielding, which is often an unavoidable necessity, especially in military and biomedical applications due to the interaction of electromagnetic fields and biological tissues. CNT composites are highly attractive in shielding due to their light weight, low cost, high strength and simple processing. One of the most important aspects is the CNTs alignment in the composites: cooperative interactions between the components can produce novel properties that do not occur individually. It was shown that the better the orientation, the higher the polymer composites' mechanical strength and shielding effectiveness (SE). Moreover, orientation of CNTs in matrix resulted in an anisotropic response of polymer composite relative to low frequency [1] and terahertz radiation [2] where it was demonstrated that the SE of polymer composites could be improved by controlling the orientation of MWCNTs. The magnetic catalytic particles embedded into the carbon nanotubes during the synthesis can lead to novel magnetic properties of the nonmagnetic polymer matrix. Many recent experiments and simulations investigated the role of catalytic particles in composite properties; SE of composites with nanotubes grown by catalytic chemical vapour deposition (CCVD) is higher than that for purified nanotubes, without contribution from the nanotube-enclosed metal catalysts. This effect was attributed to the contributions of magnetic losses and impedance match. Alternatively, the effect was attributed to increased dielectric losses because the magnetic particles content is so small that the magnetic effects are weak.

In the traditional chain “Synthesis – Characterization – Properties”, the weakest link is “Characterization”. The alignment of CNTs is mostly evaluated by the microscopy techniques like atomic force microscopy (AFM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) which provide surface information. Another approach is the use of spectroscopic techniques including polarized Raman spectroscopy, which provides quantitative but local judgements. In this work, multi-wall CNTs (MWCNTs) filled with iron nanoparticles were combined with polystyrene (PS) to evaluate interface interactions and MWCNT orientation in composite using magnetic susceptibility measurements. The measurements of magnetic moment versus field and versus temperature performed in the different directions of magnetic field produced valuable information about the orientation of MWCNTs, the arrangement of the macromolecules around them and the behaviour of catalyst nanoparticles. Comparison

of the properties of anisotropic composites containing the same MWCNT amount but prepared by different methods showed that the samples with strongly anisotropic diamagnetic properties provide anisotropic electromagnetic response and show high SE in gigahertz range.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. MWCNT synthesis

MWCNTs were produced using aerosol-assisted CCVD method in a horizontal tubular reactor, which is described in detail elsewhere [3]. Silicon substrates with a size of $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ were located in the central part of the reactor, then the reactor was pumped, filled with argon gas and heated up to 800°C . Ferrocene (2 wt. %) was dissolved in toluene and the reaction mixture was injected into the reactor with a rate of 0.14 ml/min. The pyrolysis was performed at atmospheric pressure in an argon flow ($250 \text{ cm}^3/\text{min}$) for an hour. Mössbauer spectroscopy study of MWCNTs synthesized by the same method detected three forms of iron nanoparticles, namely, two magnetic phases α -Fe and Fe_3C and one non-magnetic γ -Fe phase [4]. From the results obtained after the sample treatment with a diluted sulphuric acid, it was supposed that the α -Fe phase is mainly located close to the nanotube ends, while the γ -Fe and Fe_3C phases are inside of the channels [5].

2.2 Composite preparation

Polystyrene plates with 5 wt. % MWCNT loading were prepared using forge-rolling and stretching methods [6]. A required amount of MWCNTs separated from the silicon substrate was put into a toluene solution of polystyrene and the mixture was mechanically stirred until complete polymer dissolving. Then, the suspension was sonicated for ~ 2 min using a high-power sonic tip (200 W) with the purpose to improve the MWCNT dispersion. As produced slush was cast onto metallic substrate and dried to a viscous state at ambient conditions.

In the first batch of samples, a forge-rolling procedure was used. A composite plate was repeatedly forge-rolled along a certain direction at a linear speed of the rolls of $\sim 10\text{--}15 \text{ cm/s}$. In the second batch, a stretching procedure was used. A soft composite plate was uniaxially stretched at a heating ($\sim 70^\circ\text{C}$), which was provided by a hot air gun. A microscrew setup led to stretching of the plate in half. Finally, the composites were dried under a light load at room temperature. All the prepared plates had visually homogeneous grey colour. Investigation of the electromagnetic response of the composites prepared by the above-described techniques detected that the nanotubes have a predominant orientation in the plates [7].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Electron and atomic force microscopy

Examination of product by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) on a Hitachi S-3400N microscope revealed covering of silicon substrate by a MWCNT array (Fig. 1a). In the array, nanotubes are well aligned and oriented normally to the substrate surface (so-called nanotube forest). Cleavage of the sample for SEM study resulted in a gap between array and substrate. This is indicative of weak interaction of the constituents, which allowed separating the CNTs easily.

For high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) investigation, the MWCNTs were mixed with ethanol, and after ultrasonication the suspension was deposited on a colloidal carbon film grid. TEM images obtained on a Jeol JEM 2010 microscope showed that the CCVD product consists of MWCNTs with an outer diameter of ~20 nm (Fig. 1 b).

These processing conditions ensure a good dispersion of the MWCNTs in the polystyrene matrix as revealed by the images obtained by SEM of the composites (Fig. 1 c, d). The images were obtained from a Jeol JSM-7001F microscope.

The polystyrene/MWCNT composites were investigated in PeakForce Tapping and Semicontact Tapping modes of Scanning Probe Microscope "BRUKER Multimode 8". AFM topography revealed that MWCNTs are embedded into the polystyrene matrix, and only in rare exceptions are lying on the surface. However, Phase channel can be used to distinguish separate materials by their summarised mechanical properties. Although topography data has shown mostly flat areas not containing any MWCNTs (Fig. 1e), they were clearly distinguished in phase data channel (Fig.1f). The nanotubes are obviously oriented in same left-right direction, while only one of them, represented by a dark loop-like feature in right part of the image in Fig. 1f, is actually lying upon the surface.

<Figure 1>

3.2. Polarized Raman spectroscopy

<Figure 2>

Raman spectra in the backscattering geometry were excited with a HeNe laser (632.8 nm) at low power density ($\sim 10^4$ W/cm²) and recorded using a micro-Raman setup (Horiba Jobin Yvon LabRAM 300). A 50x microscope objective was used for focusing of the laser beam and collection of the scattered light. Polarization direction of the incident and scattered light was analysed with the polaroid quinine iodosulphate.

The Raman spectra of MWCNTs are dominated by three main peaks: a graphitic non-dispersive G-band around 1580 cm⁻¹ related to in-plane tangential stretching of the C – C bonds, a defect/disorder D band around 1331 cm⁻¹, using laser excitation of 633 nm, and second-order overtone G' at 2652 cm⁻¹. The intensity of the D band is defect dependent, and the ratio of D and G intensity I_D/I_G is used to evaluate the structural purity of graphitic materials. For carbon nanotubes, both SWNT [8] and MWNT [9], the Raman intensities are maximum when the polarization direction of the probing light is parallel to the nanotube axis (E_{\parallel}), whereas in perpendicular direction (E_{\perp}) the Raman scattering is forbidden. Raman intensities exhibit approximately $\cos^2\alpha$ -dependence in which α is the angle between the CNT axis and the polarization direction of the incident light. Remarkable difference in the intensity of Raman peaks for E_{\parallel} and E_{\perp} was reported in several studies of polymers with aligned nanotubes [10-16].

Figure 2 shows the orientation-dependent Raman spectra of the stretched (Fig. 2 a) and forge-rolled (Fig. 2 b) PS-MWNT composites with different angles between the polarization of the incidence laser light and the stretching or rolling direction. An aromatic ring breathing mode of polystyrene at 1001 cm⁻¹ is clearly seen in Fig 2, and peak intensity does not depend on laser light polarization. An orientation sensitive radial skeletal 623 cm⁻¹ line of polystyrene [17] is slightly above the noise level, so the orientation of phenyl rings in the polymer matrix is not accessible. The nanotube peaks dominate in both spectra. Fig. 2 shows significant angle-dependent changes in the Raman adsorption intensity in D, G and G' peaks, a testament to the preferential orientation of nanotubes. For the stretched composites, the changes are stronger than for the forge-rolled ones. This result indicates better nanotube alignment in the stretched composites. Here we refrain from quantitative estimation of

orientation degree of MWCNTs [18] because the intensity ratio I_{\parallel}/I_{\perp} for D, G and G' is different and varies for the measurements in several points on the same sample indicating local inhomogeneity on the micrometre scale. Similarly to Refs. [7-9], we found that the intensity ratios D_{\parallel}/D_{\perp} is higher than G_{\parallel}/G_{\perp} . The values for D_{\parallel}/D_{\perp} are around 2.8 and 1.8 for stretched and forge-rolled samples, and compared to the results [7-9] reveal highly aligned nanotubes.

The position of main peaks is stable within 1 cm^{-1} for manifold measurements on every sample. This gives the opportunity for further analysis. With regard to the raw nanotubes, all the Raman bands of the dispersed nanotubes are shifted to higher wavenumbers. We observed the upshift of the G mode, which in case of pristine nanotubes peaks at 1580 cm^{-1} , shifts to 1582 cm^{-1} for forge-rolled, and to 1584 cm^{-1} for stretched composites. The position on the G peak is affected by the nanotube-nanotube interactions [19], and the upshift may be explained by the penetration of polymer chains into nanotube aggregates during composite processing, causing debundling of nanotubes [20].

In raw nanotubes the D band is situated at 1330 cm^{-1} . It is upshifted to 1332 and 1337 cm^{-1} for the forge-rolled and stretched composites respectively. Correspondingly, the G' band shifts from its initial position 2652 cm^{-1} to 2659 and 2664 cm^{-1} . Distinct upshift of D and G' position was observed in several matrices, e.g. in poly(p-phenylene sulfide) [21], poly(vinyl alcohol) [22], polystyrene [14]. The mechanism behind the shift of the defect/disorder Raman band in CNT composites was addressed in some previous studies. In general, the upshift of the D and G' bands is caused by a modification in the C – C bond vibration resulted from local strain in CNT [23]. In case of composites, the physical mechanism behind the changes in the interatomic force constants is believed to be a consequence of the internal pressure caused by the interfacial interaction between the nanotubes and the matrix. [24, 25]. Therefore a remarkable upshift of D and G' bands in the Raman spectra demonstrates a strong filler–matrix interaction [26], particularly notable in stretched composites.

Finally, we draw attention to the I_D/I_G ratio, which equals to 0.36 in stretched composites and 0.63 in forge-rolled ones manifesting strong defectiveness of the latter. This correlates with our earlier studies [27] showing that strong forces of the rolls could damage and even break the nanotubes down to about $0.5\text{--}2.5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ in the composites prepared by the forge rolling procedure.

3.3. Thermomagnetic measurements

Measurements were done using a superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) magnetometer. Magnetic properties of samples were studied by measuring the zero field cooled (ZFC) and field cooled (FC) magnetizations at $H = 100$ Oe as a function of temperature and isothermal magnetic hysteresis loops, $M(H)$, at a given temperature. The magnetic field was varied in the range -5 T to 5 T, within the temperature range $2 - 400$ K. The magnetic moment was measured with the sensitivity of 10^{-8} electromagnetic units (emu). Figure 3 compares the results of thermomagnetic measurements on pristine MWCNT forest and the composite materials.

The results in Fig. 3, namely, increased coercive force and the difference between the ZFC and FC protocols, in a first approximation can be described by the Stoner and Wohlfarth model which accounts for the non-interacting single-domain particles with uniaxial anisotropy resulting from shape or from the magnetocrystalline anisotropy in the assumption of coherent rotation of the magnetization. Isothermal field dependencies for the nanotube forest (not shown) indicate difference between the coercive fields for in-plane field orientation compared to that for out-of-plane orientation. The obtained coercivities are larger than coercivities for bulk Fe_3C that does not exceed 100 Oe at room temperature. For the nanotube forest, the room temperature in-plane coercivity is 425 Oe whereas the out-of-plane coercivity is 500 Oe. The squariness, i.e. the ratio of remnant to saturation magnetization (M_R / M_S) is around 0.43 and 0.45 correspondingly. This is the indication of the size effect: coercivities of single domain particles are much larger than those of bulk materials. Temperature dependence of coercivity for such particles follows the law

$$H_c(T) / H_c(0) = 1 - (T/T_B)^n \quad (1)$$

where T_B is the blocking temperature for the largest particles in the system and the exponent n equals 0.5 in the Stoner and Wohlfarth model. Our experiments are perfectly fitted by the exponent $n = 0.77$ which indicates (a) distribution of easy axis [28] and (b) random assemblies where not only irreversible (switching) processes, but also reversible (rotational) processes determine the magnetization curve [29]. The 0.77 law of Formula 1 remains valid for both composites (Fig. 3a). However, in the forge-rolled composite the anisotropy towards magnetic field direction nearly disappears. In the stretched composite the difference between

the coercive forces in orthogonal direction is preserved, and, strikingly, the values of coercive force are strongly increased compared to the nanotube forest. For both directions, there is surprisingly high difference of approximately 40% between the coercive force of the embedded nanotubes and the nanotube forest. This effect should be attributed to the exchange interaction between the ferromagnetic core of the nanoparticle and the carbon shell. This interaction has the effect of the enhanced interface anisotropy, which causes a considerable increase in the coercive field of the nanoparticles.

Further information about the interactions of catalytic particle with the nanotubes and with the matrix was obtained from temperature dependencies of magnetic moment. Strong difference between zero field cooled and field cooled measurements confirms the superparamagnetic behaviour of iron nanoparticles inside the MWCNTs (Fig. 3a). A broad maximum around 340 – 380 K indicates the value of the average blocking temperature. From the position of this maximum one can estimate the average volume of nanoparticles as 1000 nm³.

<Figure 3>

Superparamagnetic behaviour is preserved in the forge-rolled composites (Fig. 3c), although it is anisotropic in respect to the field direction. However, it is not observed in the stretched composites. The increase of magnetic moment in the ZFC measurements, which is associated with the rotation of magnetic moment of each nanoparticle lying along the magnetic easy axis and energetically degenerate with respect of the parallel and antiparallel direction, is not observed any more (Fig. 3d). It was suggested that an indirect exchange coupling between magnetic nanoparticles in carbon nanotube media could be of great importance for determining the entire magnetic properties [30, 31]. Our results confirm the understanding that magnetic properties of nanoparticles inside carbon nanotubes are influenced by the nanotubes. Here we demonstrate for the first time that properties of magnetic nanoparticles are additionally influenced by the MWCNT arrangement in an organic matrix where they are embedded.

3.4. Diamagnetic susceptibility

Although it is clearly seen from Fig. 3 that magnetic susceptibility of MWCNT forest and MWCNT composites is anisotropic, the thermomagnetic measurements do not allow assessing intrinsic magnetic properties of either nanotubes or polystyrene matrix.

Ferromagnetic catalyst particles provide increased magnetization in low magnetic fields due to the contribution from initial magnetic susceptibility. We used the field dependencies of magnetization, $M(H)$ curves, taken at different temperatures and at orthogonal directions of magnetic field. The response from catalytic nanoparticles saturates at 1 T (Fig. 4 a,b), and we estimated the diamagnetic contribution from a linear diamagnetic portion of the $M(H)$ curve above 2 T. The parameter that we are interested in this section is

$$\Delta\chi = \chi_{\perp} - \chi_{\parallel} \quad (2)$$

where χ_{\perp} and χ_{\parallel} are the values of diamagnetic susceptibility for the magnetic field perpendicular and parallel to the nanotube axis.

<Figure 4>

Comparison of Fig. 4a and 4b reveals that the stretched composites show much larger anisotropy of diamagnetic susceptibility compared to the forge-rolled ones. Indeed the value $\Delta\chi$ is about $-0.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and for the forge-rolled one it four times less $-0.14 \cdot 10^{-6}$. If all the nanotubes were aligned the theoretical value $\Delta\chi$ of a composite with for 5% MWCNT loading will not exceed $-0.20 \cdot 10^{-6}$. This can be considered as the upper bound, because magnetic susceptibility of CNTs is determined by its diameter, and in our samples the diameters are diverse. For the forge-rolled samples, the $\Delta\chi$ value matches well the theoretical predictions provided that the sample contains about 80% of aligned MWCNTs. For the stretched composites the value $\Delta\chi = -0.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$ exceeds the theoretically possible one. The only plausible explanation that the nanotubes are wrapped with the polystyrene macromolecules. The benzene rings of polystyrene turn parallel to the nanotube and contribute to an additional anisotropy.

We compared the anisotropy of diamagnetic susceptibility of pure stretched PS and the stretched composites containing 1%; 2.5% and 5% MWCNTs. Pure PS demonstrate very strong differences in diamagnetic susceptibility measures in the orthogonal directions (Fig. 4c). Negative $\Delta\chi$ testifies that the chains are aligned in the stretching direction and the phenyl

rings are aligned perpendicular to it [32]. When the polystyrene is filled with the carbon nanotubes, its diamagnetic response changes not only quantitatively but also qualitatively. This is clearly seen in Fig. 4d: pure PS has a negative $\Delta\chi$ but all composites have positive. Therefore, the phenyl rings are turned parallel to the nanotubes. What might be surprising is that $\Delta\chi$ increases when the nanotube load decreases (Fig. 4d). We attribute this fact to the technological features of the stretching process in which it is difficult to achieve homogeneity of the sample. MWCNT strongly agglomerate in the process of drying the composite. The agglomeration degree in a sample with high MWCNT load is higher, and thus, most of the tensile forces are directed to the debundling of the agglomerates rather than on its reorientation. Thus, we found that excessive addition of MWCNTs give worse alignment, in contrast to the intuitive assumptions.

4. Discussion

Diamagnetic properties of MWCNT / polystyrene matrix are determined by (i) MWCNTs (ii) polystyrene matrix and (iii) interface interactions between the two components. CNTs have anisotropic diamagnetic susceptibility [33]. Polystyrene is usually considered a magnetically isotropic material. One can estimate the theoretical value of diamagnetism for the styrene molecule using the Pascal constants: $\chi = -0.53 \cdot 10^{-6}$ emu/g Oe. However, polystyrene contains aromatic benzene rings and value for the anisotropy of the diamagnetic susceptibility for the rings equals to $-1.11 \cdot 10^{-28}$ emu/molecule [34]. If for some reason all aromatic rings become oriented, it will result in anisotropic diamagnetic susceptibility $\Delta\chi = -0.86 \cdot 10^{-6}$ emu/g Oe, even exceeding those expected from the contribution of 5% MWCNT load.

Molecular dynamics simulations revealed that strong interfacial interactions exist between aromatic polymers and single-wall CNTs, and these interactions are governed by their mutual arrangement: they are maximized when the polystyrene macromolecule is stretched along the nanotube [35]. An experimental study also revealed that stretching orientation is a highly efficacious pathway to achieve interfacial enhancement in between polystyrene and MWCNTs [13]. Our measurements of anisotropic diamagnetic susceptibility correlate well with the fact that a considerable increase in the diamagnetic susceptibility and high anisotropy are typical for delocalized cyclic compounds. The structural difference between the stretched and forge-rolled compounds is shown in Fig. 5 a, b as the models of initial stages of the composite formation. In the stretching procedure, the macromolecules

have a good contact with the nanotube, and the aromatic rings are approximately parallel to the surface. The neighbouring rings in polystyrene occupy the places on the nanotube surface thus wrapping the nanotube and initiating wrapping of other molecules (Fig. 5a). In case of the disordered system formed during forge-rolling do not have strong intermolecular interactions with the nanotubes (Fig. 5b).

<Figure 5>

We now compare the electromagnetic properties of forge-rolled and stretched nanotubes. The samples (MWCNTs and composites) have been prepared using the above-described techniques, but the MWCNT loading in composites was 0.25 wt. %. Microwave response of the polystyrene/MWCNT composites was examined by a vector network analyser Agilent N5247A. Fig. 3 shows that orientation of nanotubes in polymer matrix results in anisotropic behaviour for both absorption and transmission modes. The forge-rolled composite has a negligible difference in microwave transmission (Fig. 5c) and absorption (Fig. 5e) for parallel and perpendicular orientations of the plate relative to polarization of the electric field. The stretched composite showed noticeable dependence of the transmission (40% versus 55%) and in absorption (60% versus 37%) for two electric field polarizations. Hence, we should conclude that electromagnetic properties of the prepared composites are strongly correlated with their arrangement in the matrix.

5. Conclusion

We have performed a comparative study of magnetic properties of polystyrene/MWCNT composites fabricated by forge-rolling and stretching techniques. We found that fabrication method influences the arrangement of nanotubes in polystyrene matrix, their interfacial interactions with the macromolecules. Noticeable difference in the behaviour of iron-based catalyst nanoparticles in nanotube forests and in the same nanotubes embedded in the matrix suggests that iron-filled carbon nanotubes in an organic matrix should be regarded as a 3-component interacting magnetic system. Superparamagnetic properties of iron-based catalyst nanoparticles encapsulated in the MWCNT cavities are modified in the coated nanotubes

compared to the naked nanotubes, thus confirming the theoretical predictions about the exchange interactions between carbon and magnetic metals.

Raman spectra demonstrated strong polarization dependence of the intensities of main MWCNT-related peaks testifying to alignment of the nanotubes, as well as the upshift of the peak positions which is considered as due to π - π stacking between polystyrene and MWNTs.

Diamagnetic susceptibility of composites measured parallel and perpendicular to the nanotube axis showed that for the stretched samples anisotropy was stronger than expected from the nanotubes. The findings are explained from the point of view of interfacial interactions. The aromatic rings of polystyrene stick to the honeycomb nanotubes, wrap them and coat them. This process is effective in the stretching procedure but not in a forge-rolled one. Thus, the magnetic measurements provide the information not only about the nanotube orientation but also about the arrangement of the macromolecules around the CNTs. The magnetic effect is very strong, and using the approach described here, one can easily estimate the degree of alignment and compare it to other composite properties. Susceptibility tests proved to be a penetrative and non-destructive type of measurement, accessing both the alignment of MWCNTs and the arrangement of the macromolecules around them, contributing to the optimal design and performance of nanocomposites.

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Figure captions

Figure 1. SEM image of initial array of MWCNTs vertically aligned on Si substrate (a), TEM image of MWCNTs from the array (b). SEM images of the MWCNT-polystyrene composite containing 5% MWCNTs with different magnification (c, d). AFM topological (e) and phase (f) scans of the same composite

Figure 2. Selected polarized Raman spectra of the stretched (a) and forge-rolled (b) PS-MWCNT composites with 5% load. Black lines depict parallel (E_{\parallel}) and perpendicular (E_{\perp}) orientations between the polarization of the incidence laser light and the stretching or rolling direction. Grey lines refer to intermediate angles.

Figure 3. Values of coercive force for the nanotube forest, forge-rolled and stretched composites with magnetic field perpendicular (\perp) and parallel (\parallel) to the nanotube axis (a).

Temperature dependencies of magnetic susceptibility measured in ZFC and FC regimes with magnetic field perpendicular (\perp) and parallel (\parallel) to the nanotube axis for pristine nanotube forest (b), forge-rolled (c) and stretched (d) composite.

Figure 4. Room-temperature $M(H)$ curves for the stretched (a) and forge-rolled (b) composites with 5% MWCNT loading. Symbols " \parallel " and " \perp " in (a, b) indicate orientation of MWCNTs in polystyrene matrix relative to the magnetic field. Room-temperature $M(H)$ curves for the pure stretched PS (c). Differences between the magnetic moment in the " \parallel " and " \perp " directions of magnetic field for pure PS and PS-MWCNT stretched composites with 1%; 2.5%; 5% loading.

Figure 5. Models explaining differences in magnetic susceptibility of the stretched (a) and forge-rolled (b) composites. Transmittance (c), and absorbance (d) of polystyrene/MWCNT composites produced stretching and forge-rolling methods. Symbols " \parallel " and " \perp " in (a, b) indicate orientation of MWCNTs in polystyrene matrix relative to the polarization of microwave electric field

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